

The Influence of Service Quality on Public Satisfaction Mediated by Public Trust in Baruga District, Kendari City

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Abstract

Original Research Article

This study aims to analyze the effect of service quality on public satisfaction mediated by public trust in Baruga District, Kendari City. The research method used is quantitative with data collection techniques through a survey of 384 randomly selected respondents. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS software. The results of the study indicate that service quality has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction, service quality has a positive and significant effect on public trust, public trust has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction, and trust significantly mediates the effect of service quality on public satisfaction, where public trust can strengthen the effect of service quality in increasing public satisfaction. This study provides implications that improving service quality must be accompanied by efforts to build public trust to maximize public satisfaction.

Keywords: Service Quality, Public Satisfaction, Public Trust.

I. INTRODUCTION

Public service is one of the main indicators of government success in meeting community needs. The quality of public services not only affects community satisfaction but also becomes a measure of public trust in government institutions. Good public services are expected to be able to create a society that is satisfied, feels appreciated, and has confidence in the government.

However, problems related to low service quality are still an issue that is often found, especially at the sub-district level. Baruga Sub-district, Kendari City, is one of the areas in Southeast Sulawesi province that has challenges in improving the quality of public services.

Service quality refers to the extent to which the services provided by the organizer meet the

expectations of the service recipient. According to Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988), the dimensions of service quality include tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions are important benchmarks for assessing whether public services can be considered adequate. Previous research has shown that good service quality has a direct impact on the level of community satisfaction (Zeithaml, Bitner, & Gremler, 2006). Public satisfaction, in the context of public services, is defined as the level of comfort or satisfaction of individuals with the process and results of the services they receive (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Although the relationship between service quality and public satisfaction has been widely studied, adding the role of public trust as a moderating variable requires more attention. Public trust is defined as public confidence in the ability,

integrity, and good intentions of government institutions in providing fair and transparent services (Fukuyama, 1995). This trust can strengthen or weaken the impact of service quality on public satisfaction. For example, high service quality will be more meaningful if the public has high trust in the public institution that provides the service. Conversely, if public trust is low, then good service quality may not be enough to increase public satisfaction (Kim & Lee, 2012).

In Baruga District, Kendari City, the problems that often arise are public complaints regarding the lack of responsiveness and empathy from service providers. In addition, the public also often complains about the lack of transparency in the administrative process which affects their level of trust in the local government. This condition indicates the need for in-depth research to understand how service quality affects public satisfaction by considering public trust as a moderating factor. This study aims to analyze the effect of service quality on public satisfaction in Baruga District, Kendari City, by looking at the moderating role of public trust. Understanding this relationship is expected to provide relevant policy recommendations to improve the quality of public services, build public trust, and ultimately increase public satisfaction. This study also contributes to the academic literature by exploring the role of public trust in strengthening the

influence of service quality on public satisfaction

II. Research Method

This study uses a quantitative approach to test the effect of service quality on public satisfaction mediated by public trust in Baruga District, Kendari City. The quantitative approach was chosen because it is able to measure the relationship between variables systematically and objectively through numerical data analyzed using statistical methods (Creswell, 2014).

The design of this research is descriptive quantitative and explanatory. Descriptive research is used to describe the quality of service, the level of public satisfaction, and public trust in the area. Meanwhile, explanatory research aims to identify the causal relationship between the variables studied, namely service quality, public satisfaction and public trust. This research was conducted on 384 residents of Baruga District, Kendari City who had used public services. Analysis the data used is a structural equation model with SmartPLS.

III. Result and Discuss

Based on the results of data analysis using SEM PLS, the research results are presented in Figure 1 and Table 1 as follows:

Figure 1. Analysis Result (Full Model)

Table 1. Direct and Indirect Effect

Direct Effect					
<u>Path coefficients</u>	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X1. Service Quality -> Y1. Public Trust	0.904	0.902	0.024	37.504	0.000
X1. Service Quality -> Y2. Public Satisfaction	0.538	0.534	0.096	5.623	0.000
Y1. Public Trust -> Y2. Public Satisfaction	0.410	0.411	0.097	4.216	0.000
<u>Path coefficients</u>	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Indirect Effect					
X1. Service Quality -> Y1. Public Trust -> Y2. Public Satisfaction	0.371	0.371	0.089	4.159	0.000

Based on the results of the data analysis presented in Figure 1 and Table 1, it shows that: 1. The influence of service quality on public trust obtained an original sample value of 0.904 with a P Value of 0.000 <0.05. This means that service quality has a positive and significant effect on public trust. This finding explains that the increasingly improved quality of service will encourage increased public trust in the quality of services provided by the Baruga sub-district government in Kendari City.

2. The influence of service quality on public satisfaction obtained an original sample value of 0.538 with a P Value of 0.000 <0.05. This means that public trust has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction. This finding explains that the increasingly improved public trust will encourage increased public satisfaction with the quality of services provided by the Baruga sub-district government in Kendari City.

3. The influence of public trust on public satisfaction obtained an original sample value of 0.410 with a P Value of 0.000 <0.05. This means that service quality has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction. This finding explains that increasing public trust will encourage increased public satisfaction with the Baruga sub-district government in Kendari City as a public service provider.

4. The effect of service quality on public satisfaction

mediated by public trust obtained an original sample value of 0.371 with a P Value of 0.000 <0.05. This means that service quality has a positive and significant effect on public satisfaction mediated by public trust. This finding explains that increasing service quality will encourage increasing public trust and increasing public trust will encourage increasing public satisfaction with the Baruga sub-district government in Kendari City as a public service provider.

IV. Conclusion

This study reveals that service quality has a significant effect on public satisfaction in Baruga District, Kendari City. Public trust is also proven to mediate the effect of service quality on public satisfaction, where improving the quality of public services organized by the Baruga District Government, Kendari City will significantly increase public trust in public services organized by the Baruga District Government, Kendari City, so that the impact significantly encourages increasing public satisfaction with the Baruga District Government, Kendari City as a provider and organizer of public services needed by the Baruga District Community, Kendari City.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bouckaert, G., & Van de Walle, S. (2003). Trust and the Public Sector: Is There Any Evidence for a Long-Term Decline? *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 69(2), 193-207.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Fukuyama, F. (1995). *Trust: The social virtues and the creation of prosperity*. Free Press.
- Hardin, R. (2002). *Trust and Trustworthiness*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Kim, S., & Lee, J. (2012). E-participation, transparency, and trust in local government. *Public Administration Review*, 72(6), 819-828. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2012.02593.x>
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management* (15th ed.). Pearson.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-Item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), 12-40.
- Putra, W., & Santoso, T. (2021). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Publik terhadap Kepuasan Pelayanan. *Jurnal Manajemen Publik*, 12(3), 98-112.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode penelitian kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D*. Alfabeta.
- Tjiptono, F., & Chandra, G. (2019). *Service, Quality & Satisfaction*. Andi Offset.
- Zeithaml, V. A., Bitner, M. J., & Gremler, D. D. (2006). *Services marketing: Integrating customer focus across the firm* (4th ed.). McGraw-Hill.